

Supplementary File 7: Deoxyhemoglobin Results

In contrast to the approach used for oxygenated hemoglobin (HbO₂; see the main manuscript), the decrease in cerebral oxygenation D_i for deoxygenated hemoglobin (HHb) was defined as the time point at which the polynomial regression reached its *minimal* value.

Data Screening and Diagnostics

Data screening indicated that there were four univariate outliers. These were associated with $\beta_{\text{HHb,mPFC}}$ ($k = 1$), $\beta_{\text{HHb,dIPFC}}$ ($k = 1$), and $\beta_{\text{HHb,IPC}}$ ($k = 2$) measures. The outliers were adjusted using a winsorization procedure (see Sullivan et al., 2021) until they came within the range $\pm -3.29 < z > \pm 3.29$ (see Tabachnick & Fidell, 2018).

The normality assumption was not met for D_{HbO_2} ($p < .001$) in each of the two brain regions of interest, and proved resistant to various transformations (e.g., rank-based inverse normal transformation, square-root, reflect and log/square root, and Yeo–Johnson transformation). Accordingly, the nonparametric Friedman rank sum test was employed. Finally, normality tests also indicated that β_{HbO_2} —for each of the three brain regions of interest—exhibited instances of non-normality ($p < .001$), and ordered quantile normalization transformations (Peterson & Cavanaugh, 2020) were applied to remedy this.

Decrease in Cerebral Oxygenation

The Friedman test performed on D_{HbO_2} in the mPFC showed no significant main effect of condition, $\chi^2(2) = 0.34$, $p = .844$, $W < .01$. The Friedman test performed on D_{HbO_2} in the dlPFC was also nonsignificant, $\chi^2(2) = 7.45$, $p = .024$, $W = .10$. Overall, it was evident that the delay in cerebral oxygenation decrease before volitional exhaustion was not affected by condition.

Amplitude of Activation

The oneway RM ANOVA on β_{HbO_2} in the mPFC showed no significant main effect of condition, $F(2, 20) = 0.25, p = .779, \eta_p^2 = .02$, as did the oneway RM ANOVA on β_{HbO_2} in the dlPFC, $F(1.27, 11.43) = 0.03, p = .906, \eta_p^2 < .01$, and the oneway RM ANOVA on β_{HbO_2} in the lateral parietal cortex, $F(2, 70) = 0.23, p = .797, \eta_p^2 < .01$. Overall, the results indicated that activation of the mPFC, dlPFC, and lateral parietal cortex was not influenced by condition.

References

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- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2018). *Using multivariate statistics* (7th ed.). Pearson.